

Linnæus University

Monthly Report January 2026

SENTINEL Wild Birds

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SUMMARY REPORT

1. OVERVIEW

SENTINEL Wild Birds aims to enhance the understanding of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) virus dynamics in wild bird populations by conducting active surveillance at key locations in and near Europe. These locations are divided into the following surveillance nodes: Node 1 Gulf of Finland (Finland, Estonia), Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea (Sweden, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland), Node 3 Western Black Sea (Ukraine), Node 4 Eastern Black Sea (Georgia), Node 5 Wadden Sea (the Netherlands), Node 6 Lake Constance (Germany, Austria, Switzerland), Node 7 Veneto Region (Italy), Node 8 Camargue (France), and Node 9 Gulf of Cadiz (Spain). This monthly summary provides an update on sampled wild birds as part of an early warning system to support wildlife management and disease prevention efforts. The data in this report are based on previously unpublished samples from nine nodes, collected from August 2025 to January 2026. The inclusion of samples from August and September reflects the first-time reporting of data from the Wadden Sea (Node 2), which also contributed samples from later months.

2. RESULTS

2.1 DATA COLLECTION

Since the last monthly report was published on 23rd of December 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18031042>), and as of 15th January 2026, test results have been submitted for 2,965 samples taken from 1,988 individuals representing 45 taxa from nine nodes in and near Europe (Table 1). Of the 2,965 collected samples, 859 (29%) were tracheal/oropharyngeal swabs, 815 (27%) cloacal swabs, 613 (21%) combined swabs (choana + cloacal), 555 (19%) fecal samples, 118 (4%) feather samples, and 5 (<1%) choana swabs.

Prevalence and host species sampled

The most sampled species were Mallard (686 individuals) and Black-headed Gull (379 individuals; Table 1). High bird-level prevalence in species with a sample size of at least 50 individuals was found in Mallard (22%; n=686), Ruddy Turnstone (17%, n=59), Eurasian Teal (3%, n=264), and Eurasian Wigeon (3%, n=198). Overall bird-level prevalence was 10% (192 of 1,988 individuals; Table 1).

TABLE 1 Most recently sampled individuals in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of individuals sampled in the wild, number of individuals tested positive for avian influenza virus as well as bird-level prevalence. The table includes previously unpublished samples from August 2025 to January 2026.

Group/species	Node 1 Finland		Node 2 Sweden		Node 3 Ukraine		Node 4 Georgia		Node 5 Netherlands		Node 6 Austria		Node 6 Switzerland		Node 7 Italy		Node 8 France		Node 9 Spain		Total		
	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Ind.	Pos.	Prev.
<i>Waterfowl</i>																							
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	1	7%
Tundra Bean Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	100%
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0%
Brent Goose	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	6	0	0%
Mallard	11	3	64	23	9	3	256	17	321	101	2	0	7	0	1	0	15	1	0	0	686	148	22%
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	1	8%
Gadwall	0	0	0	0	0	0	28	2	5	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	39	2	5%
Northern Pintail	0	0	2	1	0	0	6	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	1	10%
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	44%
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	0	0	2	1	4	0	121	5	71	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	198	6	3%
Eurasian Teal	1	0	0	0	4	2	20	1	27	1	0	0	2	0	112	3	98	2	0	0	264	9	3%
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0%
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0%
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	9	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	3	30%
Long-tailed Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Grebes</i>																							
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
<i>Cormorants</i>																							
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0%
<i>Hérons</i>																							
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
<i>Rails</i>																							
Water Rail	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	43	2	5%
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	13	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	31	0	0%
<i>Waders</i>																							
Pied Avocet	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
Common Ringed Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Grey Plover	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
European Golden Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0%
Ruddy Turnstone	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	10	17%
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	102	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	103	1	1%
Common Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0%
Common Greenshank	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Bar-tailed Godwit	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	2	18%
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0%
Eurasian Curlew	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Eurasian Whimbrel	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Eurasian Woodcock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0%
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0%
<i>Larids</i>																							
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	5	1	349	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	379	1	0%
Little Gull	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0%
Total	12	3	67	24	129	8	686	21	701	130	113	0	37	0	118	3	113	3	12	0	1988	192	10%

HPAI detection

Of all samples, 197 (7%) tested positive for avian influenza virus, of which 37 (1%) samples were positive for highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI; H5) virus (Figure 1; Table 2). These HPAI virus-positive samples originated from 30 Mallards in the Netherlands (week 41-48), four Eurasian Teals (two in Italy; week 52, one in the Netherlands; week 47, and one in France; week 1), one Mute Swan (week 46), one Tundra Bean Goose (week 46), and one Northern Shoveler (week 41), all three in the Netherlands. Of the 37 samples positive for HPAI virus, 27 were reported as taken from juvenile birds.

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Other subtypes

Subtyped rRT-PCR-positive samples included 13 H5 viruses with undetermined NA subtypes (eight Mallards and one Ruddy Turnstone from the Netherlands, and four Mallards from Sweden).

FIGURE 1 Sample sites in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Sample sites for the 1,988 individuals sampled in Finland, Sweden, Ukraine, Georgia, the Netherlands, Austria, Switzerland, Italy, France, and Spain. The figure includes previously unpublished samples from August 2025 to January 2026.

A weekly compilation of all 27,696 samples (positive and negative; including previously published), collected at each node from August 2024 to January 2026, can be seen in Figure 2. Proportion of positive individuals (bird-level prevalence) per week over the total project period, all nodes combined, can be seen in Figure 3. During autumn and winter 2025, there are peaks of high bird-level prevalence in August and September followed by a sustained high proportion of positive individuals until beginning of December (Figure 3).

TABLE 2 Most recently collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Total number of collected samples as well as number of samples positive for avian influenza virus. The table includes previously unpublished samples from August 2025 to January 2026.

Group/species	Node 1 Finland			Node 2 Sweden			Node 3 Ukraine			Node 4 Georgia			Node 5 Netherlands			Node 6 Austria			Node 6 Switzerland			Node 7 Italy			Node 8 France			Node 9 Spain			Total		
	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI	Samp.	Pos.	HPAI			
<i>Waterfowl</i>																																	
Mute Swan	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	14	1	1
Tundra Bean Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
Greylag Goose	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Brent Goose	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Ruddy Shelduck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	7	0	0
Mallard	22	3	0	128	23	0	18	3	0	512	19	0	321	101	30	2	0	0	7	0	0	3	0	0	30	1	0	0	0	0	1043	150	30
Domestic Mallard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22	1	0
Gadwall	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	56	3	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	67	3	0
Northern Pintail	0	0	0	4	2	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	18	2	0
Northern Shoveler	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	4	1
Eurasian Wigeon	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	2	0	8	0	0	121	5	0	71	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	204	7	0
Eurasian Teal	2	0	0	0	0	0	8	2	0	40	1	0	27	1	1	0	0	0	2	0	0	336	3	2	196	2	1	0	0	0	611	9	4
Common Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0
Red-crested Pochard	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	4	0	0
Tufted Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	9	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	3	0
Long-tailed Duck	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Grebes</i>																																	
Black-necked Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Great Crested Grebe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Cormorants</i>																																	
Great Cormorant	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0
<i>Hérons</i>																																	
Grey Heron	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
<i>Rails</i>																																	
Water Rail	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0
Common Moorhen	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	41	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	47	2	0
Eurasian Coot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	13	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20	0	0	43	0	0
<i>Waders</i>																																	
Pied Avocet	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	0
Common Ringed Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Grey Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
European Golden Plover	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Red Knot	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	33	0	0
Ruddy Turnstone	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	59	10	0
Dunlin	0	0	0	0	0	0	204	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	205	1	0
Common Sandpiper	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Common Redshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	0
Common Greenshank	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Bar-tailed Godwit	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	2	0
Numenius sp.	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Eurasian Curlew	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Eurasian Whimbrel	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Eurasian Woodcock	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	15	0	0
Common Snipe	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0
<i>Larids</i>																																	
Black-headed Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	1	0	420	0	0	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	455	1	0
Little Gull	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Total	24	3	0	134	25	0	258	9	0	1094	24	0	701	130	34	113	0	0	37	0	0	354	3	2	226	3	1	24	0	0	2965	197	37

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FIGURE 2 Weekly summary of collected samples in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In total, 27,696 samples (negative samples in blue; samples positive for avian influenza virus in orange) have been collected at nine nodes between August 2024 and January 2026, yielding 2,098 samples positive for avian influenza virus, including 88 samples positive for HPAI virus. The figures also include samples published in previous reports.

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Figure 3 Weekly bird-level prevalence of avian influenza virus in the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. Weekly prevalence of individuals positive for avian influenza virus from all nodes combined between August 2024 and January 2026, separated for each year. The figures only include bird samples (excluding mussels). The number of individuals (here: any individual bird sampled on a given day) are included at the top of the figure.

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2.2 GENOMICS SUMMARY

Since the last report was published on 23rd of December 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18031042>), and as of 15th of January 2026, five new H5 sequences have been generated from samples positive for avian influenza virus. These samples were collected from Eurasian Teal in France (Node 8 Camargue Region; N=3), as well as a Mallard and a Northern Shoveler in the Netherlands (Node 5 Wadden Sea). The majority of the sequences were of the H5N1 (N=4) and H5 (N=1) subtypes.

Genetic analysis of the haemagglutinin (HA) gene sequences from these sequences found that all belonged to the H5 clade 2.3.4.4b of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) (Figure 4A).

The majority (N=3; one from Node 5 Wadden sea and two from Node 8 Camargue Region) were of the H5 HPAI sequences DI.2.1 sub-genotype of the EA-2024-DI genotype, according to the European Union Reference Laboratory for Avian Influenza classification system (<https://github.com/izsvenezie-virology/genin2>). However, the other two H5 HPAI sequences (one from Node 5 Wadden Sea and one from Node 8 Camargue region) could not be genotyped due to missing viral genome segments. These sequences were obtained from samples collected on separate occasions across a 42-day period (11th October – 22nd November 2025) and found to be similar to other H5N1 DI.2.1 sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project from Latvia and Sweden (both Node 2 Southern Baltic Sea) (Figure 4B). Additionally, these DI.2.1 sequences collected within the project show similarity to other sequences of the same H5 genotype collected from across Europe and surrounding countries.

The Nextstrain builds are available on the SENTINEL Wild Birds Group (<https://nextstrain.org/groups/SentinelWildBirds>).

Aside from the H5 sequences, there have been six non-H5 avian influenza sequences generated from samples collected in Finland (Node 1 Gulf of Finland), all of which were from Mallards and were of the following subtypes: 1xH6N1, 3xH6N8, 1xH9N2 and 1xH12N5

This analysis is based on data obtained from the GISAID EpiFlu platform (Elbe and Buckland-Merrett 2017; Shu and McCauley 2017) up to 20th January 2026, and is accessible at <https://doi.org/10.55876/gis8.260122br>. Where sequences were included that are under a publishing embargo at the time of writing, specific permission to utilise these data was obtained from the Data Provider.

Figure 4 Phylogenetic analyses of the H5 HA sequences generated by Node 5 Wadden Sea and Node 8 Camargue Region. A. Image of the H5 HA sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project, with the 2.3.4.4b and EA-nonGsGd clades highlighted. **B.** Zoom image of the HA tree focusing on the H5 highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) clade 2.3.4.4b sequences from Node 5 Wadden Sea and Node Southern Baltic Sea and Node 4 Eastern Black Sea in relation to other sequences from Europe and surrounding countries. The sequences from the SENTINEL Wild Birds project are annotated. In **A** and **B** tip shapes are coloured according to the sampling node.

3. CONCLUSION

With close to 2,000 individual birds representing more than 40 species sampled across ten countries during the current period, the coverage of active surveillance of avian influenza viruses in wild birds in and near Europe remains substantial.

After an autumn characterised by high prevalence of avian influenza virus and multiple detections of highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) across Europe, the epidemiological situation during the winter period appears to have slowed down. The transition from autumn migration to wintering conditions is associated with reduced large-scale bird movements and fewer immunologically naïve juveniles. Together, these factors are likely to contribute to lower transmission rates and fewer new avian influenza virus detections. Still, a considerable number of positive samples have been reported since the December report, particularly from Sweden and the Netherlands, indicating ongoing circulation within wintering bird assemblages rather than a complete ending of transmission.

Among species sampled in sufficient numbers, Mallards again showed relatively high prevalence, reinforcing their central role in the transmission of avian influenza viruses. In addition, Ruddy Turnstones showed a high prevalence in samples from the Netherlands during August and September, although with a somewhat limited sample size. Although shorebirds are known to be susceptible to avian influenza viruses, comparative studies indicate that they are generally less suitable as reservoir hosts than dabbling ducks, with infection patterns strongly shaped by host ecology and phylogeny (Wille *et al.* 2023). Among shorebirds, Ruddy Turnstone is one the species most often linked with avian influenza virus. High prevalence in the species is recurrent at specific North American staging sites in spring, most notably Delaware Bay, where extreme bird densities and highly synchronised staging are thought to facilitate local amplification of mainly LPAI viruses (Hanson *et al.* 2008; Maxted *et al.* 2012). In contrast, the positive findings reported here originate from late summer and early autumn, a different phase of the annual cycle with more dispersed staging patterns. High prevalence in Ruddy Turnstones has also been documented in other smaller populations at specific occasions (Hoye *et al.* 2021). Differences in season together with known ecological differences between North American and European coastal systems, suggest that the findings in the Netherlands may reflect a transient local amplification event rather than a stable, species-specific role in virus maintenance. Nevertheless, Ruddy Turnstones in Europe warrant further investigation across seasons and sites.

Also Northern Shovelers exhibited high prevalence despite small sample sizes, suggesting that this species may be underrepresented in current surveillance efforts and could warrant increased sampling to better assess its epidemiological role. Eurasian Teals are usually sampled in large numbers and show an elevated prevalence, however, during this reporting, its prevalence remained low (N.B. the relatively high number of HPAI; Table 2).

During this period, five H5 sequences have been generated, all of which were from the 2.3.4.4b HPAI clade. These H5 HPAI sequences were all of the DI.2.1 sub-genotype, which has predominated in Europe since mid-September 2025 (EFSA *et al.* 2025), and demonstrate high similarity to sequences collected across Europe, including other sequences generated by the SENTINEL Wild Birds project. In addition to prior reports, this similarity highlights the connectivity between the active and passive sampling schemes that are ongoing within Europe.

In addition to the H5 sequences, several other subtypes were also detected, including H6, H9, and H12, which further support the data presented in previous SENTINEL Wild Birds reports as to the high subtypic diversity of influenza A viruses circulating in wild birds.

Taken together, the results from the current reporting period illustrate a seasonal transition in avian influenza virus dynamics, from widespread transmission during autumn migration to more localised circulation during the winter period. While overall activity has decreased, continued detections emphasise the importance of sustained surveillance beyond the peak migration season. Ongoing genomic analyses will provide further resolution to the processes shaping virus circulation in wild birds across Europe.

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